

Spain and artificial intelligence: installed capacities, challenges, and opportunities

España ante la inteligencia artificial: capacidades instaladas, desafíos y oportunidades

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Abstract: this research analyzes the current state and future of the installed capacities for the development of artificial intelligence (AI) in Spain. The study is justified by the growing strategic importance of AI as a driver of digital, economic, and social transformation, as well as by the scarcity of empirical analyses that address its specific evolution in the Spanish context. The main objective is to assess Spain's situation by adapting the Latin American Artificial Intelligence Index (ILIA), comparing its results with those of Chile and the Latin American average, which allows for the identification of strengths, weaknesses, and areas for improvement. The methodology combines the analysis of secondary data with qualitative primary data obtained through in-depth interviews with eight experts from the academic, public, business, and civil society sectors. The main findings of the index show that Spain significantly outperforms Latin American countries in enabling factors, R&D&I, and governance. However, weaknesses were identified in territorial coordination, citizen participation, and risk regulation. The interviews confirm an optimistic view of the future of AI in Spain, highlighting key sectors such as healthcare, education, industry, and human talent development. It is concluded that Spain has the potential to position itself as a regional and international benchmark, provided that it strengthens its institutional capacities, promotes public-private cooperation, and ensures ethical development aligned with human rights.

Keywords: AI, governance, innovation, regulation, development, ethics, data, society.

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Resumen: esta investigación analiza el estado actual y las perspectivas futuras de las capacidades instaladas para el desarrollo de la inteligencia artificial en Spain. El estudio se justifica por la creciente importancia estratégica de la IA como motor de la transformación digital, económica y social, así como por la escasez de análisis empíricos que aborden su evolución específica en el contexto español. El objetivo principal es evaluar la situación de Spain mediante la adaptación del Índice Latinoamericano de Inteligencia Artificial (ILIA), contrastando sus resultados con los de Chile y la media de América Latina, lo que permite identificar fortalezas, debilidades y oportunidades de mejora. La metodología combina el análisis de datos secundarios con datos primarios cualitativos obtenidos a través de entrevistas en profundidad a ocho expertos provenientes de los sectores académico, público, empresarial y de la sociedad civil. Los principales resultados del índice muestran que Spain supera ampliamente a los países latinoamericanos en factores habilitantes, I+D+A y gobernanza. No obstante, se identifican debilidades en la coordinación territorial, la participación ciudadana y la regulación de riesgos. Las entrevistas confirman una visión optimista del futuro de la IA en Spain, destacando sectores clave como salud, educación, industria y formación de talento humano. Se concluye que Spain tiene potencial para posicionarse como referente, siempre que refuerce sus capacidades institucionales, fomente la cooperación público-privada y garantice un desarrollo ético alineado con los derechos humanos.

Palabras clave: IA, gobernanza, innovación, regulación, desarrollo, ética, datos, sociedad.

Introduction

Generative AI, economic potential, and ethical considerations

Artificial intelligence (AI) has made remarkable progress in recent years, with an exponential impact following the emergence of generative AI (Weglarz *et al.*, 2025). These tools have become part of everyday life and general interest has skyrocketed; between 2022 and 2023, searches for generative AI grew by almost 700% (McKinsey and Company, 2024). According to Stanford University's *AI Index Report* (2025) in 2024, 78% of organizations used AI, an increase of 23 points over 2023, with investments of \$33.9 billion, 18.7% more than the previous year (Maslej *et al.*, 2025). Therefore, although it is a recent technology, its development is rapid (Navarro, 2018).

Generative AI has strong economic potential. It is projected to be an engine of global growth (Azuaje, 2021). Goldman Sachs estimates that it will raise US labor productivity by 1.5 points annually for ten years and increase global GDP by 7% (Briggs and Kodnani, 2023). Other sources suggest that by 2030, AI could add €14 trillion to the global economy and double economic growth by 2035 (Ministerio de Ciencia, Innovación y Universidades, 2019).

The impact is already evident. *Deloitte Global's 2025 Predictions Report* anticipates that 25% of companies using generative AI will implement AI agents by 2025, and 50% by 2027 (Deloitte, 2024). According to the *2025 Generative AI in Professional Services Report*, its adoption in

professional services grew from 12% to 22% in one year, while organizations with no plans to use it fell from 60% to 41% (Thomson Reuters, 2025). *The State of AI 2025* report indicates that 65% of organizations were already using generative AI on a regular basis in 2024, and that its governance is usually led by the CEO (McKinsey and Company, 2024). Despite the overall reduction in technology investment, investment in AI increased (McKinsey and Company, 2024). NTT DATA (2024) confirms that 83% of CEOs have a clear strategy, although only 49% have aligned it with their business; however, 99% plan to increase investment.

Expectations are positive: AI is projected to bring efficiency, new jobs, and improvements in most sectors (Comisión Europea, 2020; Ministerio de Ciencia, Innovación y Universidades, 2019). It could even anticipate pandemics such as COVID-19 (Robles-Fernández *et al.*, 2022). But there are also risks, such as discrimination, loss of privacy, and criminal use (Comisión Europea, 2020). Therefore, ethical and transparency standards are needed (Birkstedt *et al.*, 2023; Ministerio de Ciencia, Innovación y Universidades, 2019; Robles, 2014). Although it can benefit 134 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), it could also inhibit 59 (Vinuesa *et al.*, 2020).

In the context of technological revolution, AI has become the pillar of transformation in multiple sectors, including public administration. This has given rise to smart governance, based on data, algorithms, and citizen interaction. Cerrillo (2019) emphasizes that this form of governance is not limited to automation, but seeks more informed, agile, and fair decisions.

Smart governance and AI in Spain

However, in democracies, the use of AI faces several obstacles, including a lack of transparency. Cerrillo (2019) warns about algorithmic opacity undermining public trust by operating as a “black box.” In response to this, Cotino (2019) proposes applying five ethical principles: beneficence and non-maleficence, justice, freedom and autonomy, explainability and transparency, with empathy as an additional principle, recommending, in turn, codes of conduct and ethics committees.

These concerns open ethical and philosophical debates. De Pisón (2022) argues that legal concepts must be rethought in the face of challenges such as dystopian transhumanism, proposing disciplines such as roboethics and neuroethics. Viveros (2022) advocates for global AI governance that also holds states accountable.

In the democratic sphere, AI can enhance participation and transparency, although difficulties remain, as indicated by Moreno *et al.* (2023). Innerarity (2025), in *A Critical Theory of Artificial Intelligence*, asserts that traditional ethics are insufficient in the face of the structural goals of AI, and proposes transforming democratic institutions to integrate citizen deliberation into the design of AI systems.

Despite this, transparency and accountability remain fundamental, especially in public administration (Filgueiras, 2021). While these practices mitigate risks in companies, in the public sector they are fundamental democratic principles. Transparency promotes efficiency and institutional trust, with one of the main objectives being to make these systems understandable to both citizens and civil servants (Valero, 2019).

AI must be evaluated not only for its efficiency, but also for its respect for dignity and fundamental rights, with ethics integrated from the design stage (Martínez, 2019).

One of the persistent challenges is algorithmic opacity, especially in sub-symbolic AI. Binns (2017) recommends using more understandable models such as decision trees. However, Ananny and Crawford (2017) warn that the

visibility of the algorithm does not guarantee its understanding, and they advocate for systems adapted to social and political contexts, distinguishing between the right to know and the right to understand.

From a legal perspective, AI raises several questions about civil rights and access to information. Cerrillo (2019) analyzes cases in Spain and Italy where access to algorithms is central and refers to a decision by the Commission for the Guarantee of the Right of Access to Public Information (GAIP) in Spain that recognizes algorithms as part of the right to public information, highlighting algorithmic transparency as fundamental to democracy.

The use of Big Data also involves risks in terms of privacy and responsibility. Estupiñán *et al.* (2021) call for the establishment of robust legal frameworks that promote AI without sacrificing rights. Ponce-Cedeño *et al.* (2023) reinforce this idea, insisting on design with privacy built in from the outset and the prevention of bias, also emphasized by Cotino (2019).

Thus, regulating AI is a global challenge. Organizations such as the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development, the United Nations, and the Council of Europe have proposed regulatory frameworks for its use in public administrations. The European Union stands out for its ethical and democratic model, focused on data protection and privacy (Criado, 2021), and involves non-EU experts in its guidelines (Comisión Europea, 2020).

At the national level, the OECD noted that between 2011 and 2018, only 3% of investment in AI startups in the EU went to Spanish companies, compared to 13% in France, 14% in Germany, and 55% in the United Kingdom (Ministry of Science, Innovation, and Universities, 2019). Nevertheless, according to Roland Berger, Spain is one of the four most important countries in AI in Europe, alongside the United Kingdom, France, and Germany, accounting for 60% of the European ecosystem. However, the EU only accounts for 8% of global investment, compared to 85% for China and the US (Ministerio de Ciencia, Innovación y Universidades, 2019).

However, although the use of algorithms based on AI systems in the public sector is a growing reality, it remains an under-explored area (Criado, 2021), specially regarding assessing the current and potential development of AI in Spain and understanding the factors that drive or limit it. Therefore, this study—whose main objective is to analyze the current and future situation of the installed capacities for AI development in Spain—aims to take a step forward in filling this gap in the literature by providing empirical evidence on the subject.

Materials and method

Objectives

This study aims to analyze the current and future situation of installed capacities for the development of artificial intelligence in Spain. To this end, the following objectives are proposed:

- i) Develop an index to assess the state of AI in Spain by adapting the Latin American Artificial Intelligence Index (ILIA) developed by the National Center for Artificial Intelligence of Chile (CENIA).
- ii) Compare the development of AI in Spain with Chile and the LATAM average included in the CENIA study to observe Spain's relative position and its areas of strength and weakness.

Adaptation of the ILIA to the Spanish case

The ILIA is a public good promoted by CENIA and ECLAC, with the support of organizations such as the Development Bank of Latin America and the Caribbean (CAF), the Inter-American Development Bank (IDB), the Organization of American States (OAS), and UNESCO.

The index is composed of three fundamental quantitative dimensions: i) enabling factors, which measure technological infrastructure, access to open data, and the availability of specialized human talent, and allow for the projection of AI potential in each nation; ii) R&D&I, focused on the advancement of research, development, and adoption of AI technologies in the public, private, and academic sectors, which affects the global competitiveness of countries; and iii) governance, which assesses the degree of institutional maturity in public policies and regulations for the ethical and sustainable development of AI (ILIA, 2024).

In addition to these three quantitative dimensions, there are two other qualitative and prospective dimensions proposed by CENIA: iv) the future of AI, measured by expert perception, and v) social perception of AI.

In its second edition, the ILIA maintained these five dimensions, although it introduced new indicators and sub-indicators to achieve a more complete view of AI development in the region. In addition, it received support from new international actors such as the European Union, through the EU-LAC Digital Alliance, and from technology companies such as Google, Microsoft, and Amazon Web Services (AWS), which enriched its analysis (ILIA, 2024). In the case of Spain, the three quantitative dimensions were applied using primary sources of public information (Table 1).

Table 1
Primary sources for the dimensions

Dimension	Sub dimension	Indicators	Proposed sub-indicators	Normalized score for Spain	Source	
Enabling factors	Infrastructure	Connectivity	Percentage of population using the internet.	95.40	https://bit.ly/4nC6fbI	
			Average mobile download speed.	121.60	https://bit.ly/4n63G1G	
			5G implementation.	Source Not comparable	https://bit.ly/3IppMwK	
			Mobile network coverage.	99.70	https://bit.ly/41TmUio	
			Households with internet access.	96.40	https://bit.ly/48orSaK	
			Active mobile broadband subscriptions. mobile broadband.	94.77	https://bit.ly/48kzMSD	
			Fixed broadband subscriptions.	112.10	https://bit.ly/46sZMsz	
			Average fixed broadband download speed.	87.5	https://bit.ly/41Pw1Ri	
			Average latency.	99.52	https://bit.ly/4grRTIj	
			Basic fixed broadband basket.	105.05	https://bit.ly/4megsd1	
			Computing	Cloud.	32.5	https://bit.ly/466p7tq
				HPC infrastructure capacity.	200.00 ¹	https://bit.ly/3VOi1Uf
				Certified data centers	16.67	https://bit.ly/48fjcU7
				IXP.	42.65	https://bit.ly/3Vlc7db
	Secure Internet servers.	225.28		https://bit.ly/466pe8k		
	Devices	Households with computers.	82.27	https://bit.ly/4mdNNVv		
		Smartphone affordability.	ND	ND		
		IPv6 adoption.	18.47 ²	https://bit.ly/46ocpFd		
	Data	Data Barometer Data	Availability.	46.62	https://bit.ly/3IpLYXE	
			Capabilities.	74.41	https://bit.ly/482Q4Qb	
			Governance.	58.53	https://bit.ly/4nShpt1	
			Use and impact.	20.62	https://bit.ly/4polTJI	
	Human Talent	AI literacy	Early science education.	152	https://bit.ly/4pphMMV	
			Early education in AI.	80.00	https://bit.ly/42wYRWC	
			English language skills.	57.58	https://bit.ly/4pqyxaF	
		Professional training in AI	AI skills penetration.	ND	Información insuficiente	
			STEM graduates.	55.75	https://bit.ly/4pl9pCI	
Talent Advanced		Master's Programs in AI at QS Ranking Universities.	60.23	Own elaboration		
	PhD programs in AI at universities in the QS Ranking.	78.51	Own elaboration			

Dimension	Sub-dimension	Indicators	Proposed sub-indicators	Note of Spain	Source
	Talent Human	Talent Advanced	Master's Programs in AI. Accredited Universities.	74.62	Own elaboration
			Doctoral Programs in AI. Accredited Universities.	82.45	Own elaboration
Research, adoption, and development	Research	Research	Publications on AI.	452.23	https://bit.ly/4mjDhvU
			Active researchers in AI.	ND	ND
			Productivity of researchers in AI.	ND	ND
			Impact of AI research.	38.78	https://bit.ly/46hGshH
			Presence of AI research centers.	80.00	Own elaboration
			Proportion of female authors in AI.	74.84	https://bit.ly/46ojA02
			Consistent research in AI.	ND	ND
			Participation in main track of A+ conferences.	ND	ND
	Participation in side events at A+ conferences.	ND	ND		
	R&D	Open Source Productivity Development	Open Source Productivity.	ND	ND
			Open Source Quality.	ND	ND
		Innovation	Number of Patents.	212.56	https://bit.ly/3VQJNiV
			Number of private investments.	263.93	https://bit.ly/4meygEP
			Total estimated value of private investment.	362.22	https://bit.ly/4pE8pJE
			AI companies.	187.33	https://bit.ly/3K2DnL7
			Unicorn companies.	215.29	https://bit.ly/3IezrGE
			Research and development expenditure as a proportion of GDP.	124.28	https://bit.ly/4pp9gxB
	Application development.	93.00	https://bit.ly/46iNByf		
	Entrepreneurial environment.	60.56	ND		
	Adoption	Industry	Workers in the high-tech sector.	48.35	https://bit.ly/3ViWl2o
Medium and high technology manufacturing.			ND	ND	
Proportion of added value of medium-tech manufacturing and high technology manufacturing in total added value.			136.61	https://bit.ly/3Vle21n	
Government		Digital Government.	98.72	https://bit.ly/4nxdph1	
Governance	Vision and Institutional Framework	AI Strategy	Existence of the strategy.	100	https://bit.ly/47Lpaw2
			Presence of institution responsible for the implementation.	100	https://bit.ly/41XtS66
			Presence of evaluation mechanisms.	100	https://bit.ly/41QyevJ
			Presence of mechanisms for inter-institutional coordination mechanisms of Ethics and governance of AI.	100	https://bit.ly/48i3N5u

Di- men- sion	Sub dimen- sion	Indicators	Proposed sub-indicators	Note for Spain	Source
Governance	Vision and Institutional framework	AI Strategy	AI Infrastructure and Technology.	100	https://bit.ly/4popCXj
			Capacity Building.	100	https://bit.ly/41SRpoF
			Data.	100	https://bit.ly/48eR7wg
			Digital Government.	100	https://bit.ly/4gyQDmY
			Industry and Entrepreneurship	100	https://bit.ly/3K5ihM7
			R&D.	100	https://bit.ly/3K4nqE3
			Regional and International Cooperation.	100	https://bit.ly/4n24SCV
		Community involvement	Citizen participation.	60	https://bit.ly/3I9C3Wd
			Multistakeholder methodology.	20	³
	Institutional nality	Existence of the institution.	100	https://bit.ly/42yqD57	
	International	Participation in defining standards	Participation in ISO.	100	https://bit.ly/48fIDWL
		Participation in interna- tional orga- nizations	Participation in international committees.	100	https://bit.ly/3K2Idbi
	Regulation	AI regulation	Risk mitigation.	0	https://bit.ly/4gpEd0x
		Cyber security	Cybersecurity index.	101.99	https://bit.ly/41RBxTw
		Ethics and Sustai- nability	Civil and Political Rights Data Protection and Privacy (GIRAI).	100.83	https://bit.ly/3IoCOuw
Technical Standards Security, Accuracy and Reliability (GIRAI).			136.2	https://bit.ly/47FP5Fe	
Sustainability	Sustainability	108.11	https://bit.ly/46CMsCZ		

Note. ¹ Despite being the highest result, we limited the data to twice the maximum obtained in the ILIA 2024 country data. / ² LACNIC does not produce statistics for Spain, so Google's statistics are used. / ³ No information has been published by the government on the creation of the strategy. / ND = Data not available.

Prepared internally based on ILIA (2024).

The methodology used by CENIA (2023) was followed, which establishes the need to homogenize heterogeneous data. This was done by recoding the raw values of each sub-indicator on a scale of 0 to 100. Replicating the proposal of these authors for Spain, and thus

following the methodology used in the Government AI Readiness Index by Oxford (Fuentes *et al.*, 2024) and in The Global AI Index (Tor-
toise, 2024), the Min-Max criterion was used to normalize the collected data. Two types of minimums and maximums were used: feasible

(for categorical sub-indicators) and observed effective (for continuous sub-indicators). Thus, when the possible extreme values were known, these were used; otherwise, the values observed in the ILIA 2024 were used.

The sub-indicators were aggregated by assigning them the same weight, given the lack of evidence to prioritize some over others. This logic was maintained throughout the entire structure of the index: all sub-indicators have the same weight within an indicator, all indicators have the same weight within a sub-dimension, and each sub-dimension counts equally within its dimension.

However, applying the ILIA 2024 to Spain posed several challenges. First, adapting a regional methodology designed for Latin America to a European country proved complex, as many ILIA indicators are based on regional statistics that do not have a direct correspondence in Spain. Furthermore, as it is a comparative index in which the worst-performing country scores 0 and the best-performing country scores 100, in some cases it was not possible to calculate a score for Spain, even with data available, due to a lack of transparency in the comparative data. Despite meetings held with CENIA, it was not possible to achieve full comparability of the data.

However, the level of synchronization was high: 90.32% in the enabling factors dimension, 65.21% in R&D&I, and 100% in governance. The overall synchronization average reached 85.52%, which allows us to conclude that the data generated is robust and comparable with the ILIA results.

Regarding the fourth dimension—perceptions about the future of AI—eight semi-structured interviews were conducted with experts from academia, business, the public sector, and civil society in Spain between March and July 2024. The interviewees were: a professor of constitutional law with experience at the Spanish Data Protection Agency (interview 1); an associate professor at the Open University of Catalonia (interview 2); a technical director in the field of technology (interview 3); a pro-

fessional in digital strategy and AI from an autonomous community (interview 4); a digital transformation manager in the Region of Murcia (interview 5); a professional in the area of digitization in the judicial system (interview 6); an expert in digital rights and member of the Spanish Association for Artificial Intelligence (interview 7); and a consultant specializing in AI (interview 8).

The audio recordings of the interviews were transcribed and analyzed using open-source AI tools and/or tools developed by the researchers involved. The interviewees were then segmented using deep neural networks, based on the proposal by Bredin *et al.* (2020) and Bredin and Laurent (2021), which was combined with the extraction of vector representations (embeddings) from the interviewees' texts (Jacob de Menezes-Neto and Clementino, 2022).

Likewise, unsupervised clustering of the textual passages was performed based on a TF-IDF score, ranging from 0 to 1, with the aim of identifying the main groups of words from bigrams (Grootendorst, 2022). To this end, human analysis and the definition of stopwords obtained in the previous stages were considered to guarantee the quality and accuracy of the information.

Finally, the fifth dimension—social perception of AI—was evaluated through Study 3495 “Artificial Intelligence” by the Sociological Research Center (CIS, 2025), conducted from February 6 to 15, 2025. This survey, representative of the Spanish population over the age of 18, was conducted with a confidence level of 95.5% and a margin of error of $\pm 1.6\%$ under the assumption of simple random sampling. Thanks to this, the data can be extrapolated to Spanish society as a whole and accurately capture the general perception of AI among citizens.

Results and discussion

Social perception of AI in Spain

We analyze the dimension of the ILIA that this study does not address with primary data, i.e., social perception, using Study 3495 “Artificial Intelligence” from the Sociological Research Center (CIS, 2025) to analyze how Spaniards perceive AI and the technological advances associated with it.

According to the data, 96.4% of the population recognizes that technological advances are generating profound changes. This transformation arouses ambivalent emotions: uncertainty (67.2%) and interest (68.3%) predominate, followed by concern (58.4%) and fear (34.4%). These emotions are reflected in the most frequent conceptual associations with technology, such as “power,” “progress,” “dependence,” and “risk,” all of which score highly in terms of their connection with AI.

When it comes to privacy and the use of personal data, 77.2% of respondents consider internet privacy to be “very important.” However, there is notable concern about the use of data by private companies (77% are quite or very concerned) and, to a lesser extent, by public institutions (59.2%). In addition, the vast majority fear possible negative consequences: 89.7% believe that their data may be used without their consent, and more than 85% fear its commercial use or even becoming victims of fraud.

Added to this concern is the perception of insufficient regulation: 77.2% believe that there is no adequate regulatory framework for data collection and use, and 74.2% believe that privacy policies are unclear. As a result, there is strong social consensus on the need to regulate AI: more than 92% support establishing regulations on its use, programming, and transparency in its application by companies.

Although 92.3% have heard of AI, its everyday use remains limited. ChatGPT is the best-known tool (41.1%), but only 16.7% of its users

use it on a daily basis. AI generates more intensely negative emotions than technology in general: uncertainty (75.7%) and concern (69.6%) stand out, while optimism and confidence are in the minority.

Therefore, citizens are reluctant to engage in everyday interactions with AI, such as robotic medical operations or autonomous cars, and perceive positive effects mainly in sectors such as health, industry, and the environment, while fearing harm to employment, artistic creation, and security.

Enabling factors, R&D&I, and governance

Within the framework of the comparative study developed from ILIA 2024, the case of Spain is analyzed as a reference case outside the Latin American region, allowing for an assessment of its relative situation with respect to Latin America as a whole. The analysis is structured around the three quantitative dimensions of the index: enabling factors, research, development, and adoption (R&D&I), and governance, highlighting the European country’s outstanding position in the regional context.

The first dimension addressed is that of enabling factors, considered the most extensive in the index, as it contains a total of 31 indicators. This dimension evaluates the installed capacity of countries to develop robust artificial intelligence ecosystems, focusing on aspects such as technological infrastructure, data availability, connectivity, and human capital. As shown in Table 2, Spain achieves an average score of 75.86 out of 100, significantly higher than the Latin American average and the performance of Chile, the country with the highest score in the region. This result does not necessarily mean that Spain obtains the best value in all indicators, but rather that its score far exceeds the maximum values obtained within Latin America in many of them.

Table 2
Iliia 2024 for Chile, LATAM, and Spain

Dimensions	Sub-dimension	Indicators	Weight	Chile	LATAM	Spain	
Enabling factors Enabling	Infrastructure	Connectivity	50%	87.55	57.12	101.34	
		Computing	25%	44.26	21.76	103.42	
		Devices	25%	49.41	36.47	50.37	
	Infrastructure score			45%	67.19	43.12	89.11
	Data	Data Barometer	100%	48.32	35.76	50.04	
	Data Score			25%	48.32	35.76	50.04
	Human Talent	AI Literacy	40%	84.62	57.90	96.52	
		Professional training in AI	30%	65.80	43.49	55.75	
		Human Talent advanced	30%	69.04	11.69	73.95	
	Human Talent Score			30%	74.30	39.71	77.51
Enabling Factors Score			40%	64.60	40.26	75.86	
Research, development, and adoption	Research	Research	100%	76.85	41.43	161.46	
	Research score			40%	76.85	41.43	161.46
	R&D	Innovation	50%	67.54	31.57	186.66	
		Development	50%	15.11	20.93	212.56	
	R&D score			30%	75.60	42.53	199.61
	Adoption	Industry	60%	59.52	54.29	92.48	
		Government	40%	92.37	69.65	98.72	
Adoption Score			30%	72.66	60.44	94.97	
Research, Development, and Adoption Score			35%	75.21	47.46	152.96	
Governance	Vision and Institutional Framework	AI Strategy	50%	100	33.33	100	
		Involvement of society	25%	100	19.08	40	
		Institutionality	25%	100	21.05	100	
	Vision and institutionality score			50%	100	26.70	85
	International	Participation in standard setting	50%	0	13.16	100	
		Participation in international organizations	50%	100	92.11	100	
		International score			20%	50	52.63
	Regulation	AI regulation	20%	100	47.37	0	
		Cybersecurity	30%	71.25	49.85	101.99	
		Ethics and sustainability	50%	74.70	41.71	115.04	

Dimensions	Subdimension	Indicators	Weight	Chile	LATAM	Spain
	Score Regulation		30%	78.73	45.28	88.11
Governance Score			25%	83.62	37.46	88.93
ILIA 2024			-	73.07	42.08	106.11

Note. Prepared internally based on ILIA (2024).

A more disaggregated analysis reveals particularly strong performance in indicators related to digital infrastructure—connectivity, computing, and cloud services—although the subcomponent of devices slightly weighs down the average. Nevertheless, the overall infrastructure component continues to show highly favorable results. For several indicators, although it has not been possible to calculate exact scores due to a lack of detailed information or operationalization issues, relevant data has been collected, such as the number of supercomputers according to the *Top500.com* ranking, data centers certified by the *Uptime Institute*, and internet exchange points (IXPs) according to *Packet Clearing House*.

In terms of data availability and human capital, the results are equally encouraging. Although certain gaps have been identified in the latter component due to the difficulty in calculating some indicators, a relevant estimate has been made by counting 43 master's degrees in artificial intelligence offered by the 35 Spanish universities that appear in the QS 2024 ranking. Although these data could not be translated into a definitive score, their compilation reflects an active academic ecosystem in specialized AI training.

The second dimension of the ILIA focuses on research, development, and adoption (R&D&A) capabilities, projecting a country's future potential in the field of AI. In this section, Spain stands out even more: its weighted average exceeds 100, indicating that, in several indicators, it comfortably surpasses the best performance recorded within the Latin American environment. This situation reflects the structural differences

between the European science and innovation ecosystem and the Latin American one, even though Spain's R&D spending is moderate compared to the European Union average.

Breaking down this dimension, there is an advantageous position in research and, especially, in development. In the latter case, the indicators for technological innovation and patents reflect significant differences compared to Latin American countries: for example, the number of AI-related patents in Spain is four times that of Chile. In terms of innovation, the relative advantage is also notable, with Spain practically doubling the highest scores in Latin America. Furthermore, in both the industrial and government sectors, the level of adoption and digitization is high and reinforces the country's competitive profile.

The third dimension, governance, introduces a political-institutional analysis of the AI ecosystem, considering whether public policies and the legislative framework favor an environment conducive to the ethical, safe, and stable development of this technology. In this area, Spain also scores high, reaching an average of 88.93 out of 100. The recent National Artificial Intelligence Strategy, published in May 2024, obtains the highest score in the section corresponding to strategic design. This strategy incorporates important institutional elements, such as the creation of the Spanish AI Supervision Agency and an Advisory Council made up of international experts. Likewise, an Interministerial Commission is established to coordinate digitization within the General State Administration (AGE).

However, there are weaknesses in this governance. First, the strategy lacks robust accounta-

bility and evaluation mechanisms, a weakness that is understandable given its incipient nature but relevant in terms of effective governance. Second, there is no clear coordination with the autonomous communities, which is a problem in a country with such a marked model of administrative decentralization. Even more relevant is the lack of social participation in the development of the strategy: there is no evidence that social actors have been consulted, nor has a committee or forum been established to bring together civil society, academia, the private sector, and other stakeholders. This shortcoming contravenes one of the guiding principles of the ILIA, which advocates for participatory and multisectoral governance.

In terms of international outreach, Spain ranks among the highest: it actively participates in the ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 42 committee on AI, is a signatory to the Council of Europe Convention on AI and Human Rights, and has endorsed the Ibero-American Charter on AI in Public Administration. However, its score in the regulation subcomponent is slightly lower (88.11 out of 100) due to the absence of specific risk mitigation measures within the national strategy, an aspect that will be important to improve in the immediate future.

Comparing the results, Spain shows a clear structural advantage over Latin America and, especially, over Chile, in the three components

of the index analyzed. In enabling factors, it doubles the regional average, excelling in connectivity, data, and human capital. In R&D&I, although it is not considered qualitatively different, its indicators place it well above Latin American countries, allowing it to lead cooperation in artificial intelligence. In governance, it also significantly outperforms the region, particularly in vision and institutionality. Only in the latter aspect does Chile come close to Spanish levels, but in general, Spain maintains a leading position in all areas evaluated.

The future of AI: expert perception

In order to gain insight into the future of AI in Spain from the perspective of experts in the field, a total of eight in-depth interviews were conducted. The interview script was structured in four blocks: 1) impacts and challenges, 2) the future of AI, 3) ethics and regulation, and 4) collaboration and future research.

Regarding Spain's role at the international level, it was possible to observe how most of the interviewees point to Spain as a benchmark for Latin America (interviews 1, 2, 7) that is emerging as a key player (interviews 3, 4, 5)—see P1, Figure 1—.

Figure 1
AI in Spain

Q1 What role do you think Spain plays internationally in terms of AI research and development?

Q2. What are the four areas in which AI R&D&I and entrepreneurship efforts should focus in Spain?

Q3. What are the four main challenges Spain will face in developing AI over the next five years?

Q4. What is your opinion on the importance of collaboration between the public, private, and academic sectors in the development of AI in Spain?

Spain is making decisive progress in positioning itself as a relevant player in the development and regulation of AI in Europe. This momentum is observed in initiatives such as the National Artificial Intelligence Strategy (ENIA), the creation of the Spanish AI Supervision Agency (AESIA), and test environments (sandboxes), designed to prepare for the implementation of the European AI Regulation (interview 7). These actions have attracted international interest, consolidating Spain's position as a relevant technical and regulatory partner in Europe.

Interviewees 2 and 4 highlight that Spain has a promising technological infrastructure. Since 2018, through the Secretariat of State for Digital Advancement (SEDIA), public policies have been promoted to strengthen the technological ecosystem (interview 1). In addition, Spain has actively participated in European debates on digital rights and AI ethics. However, both Spain and the European Union face a historic gap in R&D&I investment compared to powers such as US and China (interview 4). In this regard, interviewee 2 stresses the need to increase investment in digital technologies, promote innovation, and consolidate a competitive business.

The impacts of AI are already seen, although still not very visible to the general public. According to the interviewees, public administrations and companies are implementing AI tools to improve processes and personalize services. Interview 5 mentions sectors such as healthcare, education, mobility, and entertainment, where

AI is already helping to improve access and user experience.

Based on the analysis of the P2 bigram (Figure 1), climate emergency, health, education, and industry are identified as priority areas. In the case of climate change, AI makes it possible to predict fires or droughts through massive data analysis. In education, interview 1 mentions transformations in teaching methods, while interviews 3 and 5 advocate for accessible tools and curricula adapted to the digital age.

In health, AI is revolutionizing the diagnosis and treatment of diseases through predictive algorithms and image analysis. In the workplace, AI is transforming professional profiles, especially in data science and technology. Although its impact on some services is still limited, phenomena such as "digital nomads" show a change in progress. Despite fears about automation, interviewees compare this transition to the end of the industrial era (interview 2).

Regarding the challenges (P3, Figure 1), the interviewees agree on three priorities: improving technological infrastructure, adapting training to the new labor market, and strengthening the innovation ecosystem. They also highlight the importance of data networks and educational programs, as proposed by Salvador and Ramió (2020).

There is moderate optimism about the future of AI in Spain. If investments in infrastructure, education, and public policies are consolidated, Spain could become a global benchmark and a

bridge between Europe and Latin America. To achieve this, it will be essential to overcome bureaucratic rigidity and adopt a more agile vision (interviews 1 to 5). Interviewee 2 proposes three lines of action: financing knowledge, retaining talent through quality jobs, and participating in international networks.

In terms of regulation and ethics, interviews 3 and 4 value the European approach to risk management, although they warn of the need for flexible frameworks. Interview 5 highlights that trust in AI will depend on principles such as transparency, auditability, and security. The PIO model of the Observatory of Ethics in AI (OEIAC) is mentioned, and cross-disciplinary training in digital ethics is advocated.

Finally, the interviews (P4, Figure 1) highlight the importance of cooperation between the public, private, and academic sectors, as no single actor has sufficient capabilities on its own. Interview 2 emphasizes the improvement of collaboration mechanisms and knowledge transfer, as well as citizen inclusion in the formulation of AI policies to ensure their legitimacy.

Future priorities include health, education, labor transformation, basic research, and security, reflecting concerns about ethical risks and disorganized implementation, as stated by Cotino (2019).

Conclusions

This research examines Spain's current and future capabilities for AI development, using data from the Latin American Artificial Intelligence Index (ILIA) adapted to the Spanish context and interviews with eight experts in the field. The analysis focused on three dimensions: enabling factors, R&D&I, and governance.

In terms of enabling factors, which include technological infrastructure and human capital, Spain performs well, with notable progress in creating conditions conducive to AI development. In the R&D&I dimension, the country maintains a competitive position in Europe thanks to relevant projects led by the public, private, and academic sectors. In governance, although there are solid regulatory framework-

ks and favorable public policies, there is a lack of data on citizen participation in institutional processes.

The interviews with experts were grouped into four areas: impacts and challenges, the future of AI, ethics and regulation, and collaboration and research. The experts view the ENIA and other digitization initiatives positively, although they recognize that Spain is still far from global leadership compared to countries such as the US and China. The priority areas identified for AI development were health, education, industry, and talent training, but several difficulties remain related to infrastructure and the need to promote inclusive governance aligned with human rights.

One limitation of the research identified was the need to adapt the ILIA due to the absence of some specific indicators available for Spain. Likewise, regarding the interview phase, increasing the number of interviewees would have allowed for a broader and more representative range of opinions to be obtained.

For a future stage in the research agenda, it is recommended that the comparative analysis of the ILIA and its dimensions be extended to other European Union countries. It is also suggested that a greater number of interviews with experts be included by incorporating voices from other countries and multilateral organizations, with the aim of enriching the understanding of the context, challenges, and opportunities related to the dissemination and use of AI.

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